

Supplementary data and figures

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The effect of ageing on bonding performance of plasma treated beech wood with urea-formaldehyde adhesive

Research part: Results and discussion – XPS spectra

Representative high-energy resolution O 1s survey spectra acquired with XPS on aged, fresh, untreated and plasma treated beech wood are presented in Fig. S1.

Fig. S1 Representative XPS high-energy resolution O 1s spectra on aged (-A) and fresh untreated (UT) and plasma treated (PTd) beech wood.

Summarized data of high resolution C 1s spectra components acquired with XPS, including the position and the full width at half maximum (FWHM) are presented in Table S1.

Table S1 Binding energy (eV) and Full Width at Half Maximum (FWHM) in eV of components C1-C4 used for deconvolution of XPS spectra C 1s

Sample type	C 1s component							
	C ₁ [eV]		C ₂ [eV]		C ₃ [eV]		C ₄ [eV]	
	Energy	FWHM	Energy	FWHM	Energy	FWHM	Energy	FWHM
Cellulose	284.4	1.6	286.3	1.6	287.7	1.6	288.8	1.6
UT-A	284.7	1.5	286.4	1.5	287.8	1.5	288.8	1.5
PTd-A	284.5	1.5	286.1	1.5	287.3	1.5	288.7	1.5
UT	284.5	1.5	286.0	1.5	287.2	1.5	288.6	1.5
PTd	284.7	1.5	286.3	1.5	287.8	1.5	289.1	1.5